

EFFECT OF FIN-TECH ADOPTION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF RICE FARMERS IN ANAMBRA STATE NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Financial technology has been identified as having great potential to enhance agricultural growth and development, but the constraints associated with its adoption are enormous for poor smallholder farmers. Thus, this study examined the effect of fin-tech adoption on the performance of rice farmers in Anambra state, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling method was used. Four Local Government Areas (LGAs) with the highest rice cultivation were purposively selected. Two villages were randomly selected from the LGAs, of which 13 farmers were randomly selected. Totaling 104 farmers in all. Data was collected with a well-structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive: mean, frequency and composite score; inferential statistics: T-test and logit regression model. The results showed that the farmers were aware of digital banking services with a mean awareness ranking of automated machine ($\bar{x}=3.11+0.40$). There is a significant difference in the rice yield of fin-tech adopters and non-adopters at 1% significance level. Determinants of adoption of fin-tech@_{s%} were age, household size, farm size remittances and cooperative membership. The study recommends provision of required amenities for effective adoption of fin-tech.

Keywords: Financial technology, adoption, rice farmers' performance, logit

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is one of the sub-Saharan African countries of which agriculture was the backbone of her economy before the oil boom of 1970s (Komolafe and Adeoti, 2018; Gbughemobi *et al*, (2021). Agriculture in Africa has a massive social and economic footprint; more than 60% of the populations of Sub-Saharan Africa are

smallholder farmers, and about 23% of Sub-Saharan Gross Domestic Product (GDP) comes from agriculture Goedde, *et al*, (2019). Agriculture contributed about 22.86% of Nigeria's GDP in 2017 (National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 2018). The agriculture sector plays a crucial role in the economic development of many countries, and rice farming stands

out as one of the most significant agricultural activities globally. However, rice farmers often face numerous challenges that hinder their productivity and overall performance. In recent years, financial technology (fin-tech) solutions emerged as potential tools to address these challenges and enhance the efficiency of rice farmers. Financial technology is used to describe new technology that seeks to improve and automate the delivery and use of financial services. Fin-tech offers innovative financial services and technologies that can improve access to credit, market information, and risk management tools for farmers (McIntosh and Mansini 2018) It can raise income and improve food security for 80% of the world's poor, who live in rural areas and work mainly on farms.

The potential for digital financial services to increase growth in Africa, particularly among excluded segments of the population, is substantial. Financial technology (Fin-tech) is generating new ways to target and collateralize credit, to price and spread risk, and to organize agricultural value chains. Agricultural Development Bank working paper, authored by McIntosh and Mansini, (2018) report showed that digital payment systems could close 40% of the unmet need for payment services and 20% of the need for credit. According to Ernst & Young (2019), Global Fin-tech Adoption Index in 2019 showed two-thirds of consumers utilize at least two or more fin-tech services, and those consumers are increasingly aware of fin-tech as a part of their daily lives. The components of fin-tech include (Mobile Banking, Mobile money/Online Payments, Digital Lending and Crowdfunding, Robo-Advisory, Blockchain and Cryptocurrencies,

Insurtech, Regtech and so on. Information and communication technology is changing agriculture in many dimensions beyond financial services, ICTs contribute to improving youth livelihoods, agricultural modernization and creating benefits throughout value chains, especially through increased access to more effective information via many smartphone apps (Vives, 2017; Gbughemobi, *et al.*, (2021). Mobile banking and mobile money play a crucial role in advancing fin-tech agriculture and driving its transformation. Firstly, these technologies promote financial inclusion by providing farmers and stakeholders in the agricultural sector with access to formal financial services. In many developing countries, traditional banking services are often limited or inaccessible in rural areas. By leveraging mobile banking, farmers can now have a digital wallet and access banking services through their mobile phones. This enables them to save money securely, access credit for investment in agricultural activities, and manage their finances efficiently, ultimately improving their financial well-being. Mobile banking platforms facilitate seamless and efficient transactions within the agricultural value chain. Farmers can receive payments directly to their mobile wallets, eliminating the need for cash transactions, which are often time-consuming and prone to risks. Mobile phones can provide the infrastructural backbone required by Fin-tech services to reach the marginalized populations. As opined by Abdul-Rahaman, & Abdulai, (2022) mobile phones can best be used for sustaining agricultural development when accompanied by complementary facilities, especially electricity among others, Mobile technology also provides a novel

impetus to interact with the written word and so can provide a platform to promote literacy Abdul-Rahaman, & Abdulai, (2022). The advent of mobile money further extends the possibilities of a mobile phone, providing potential for savings (Mbiti and Weil 2011), and eases the sending of remittances and risk pooling within social networks (Jack and Suri 2014). Mobile money transactions among Farmers can provide several benefits and offer significant opportunities for inclusive value chain development. Generally, besides providing opportunities for savings, especially in socially volatile and risky environments (Beck *et al.*, 2018), it allows for a reliable money transfer between value chain actors, reduces transaction costs, and facilitates market exchange (Jack & Suri, 2011; Abdul-Rahaman, & Abdulai, 2022). Mobile money technology presents several advantages for smallholder farmers and agribusiness companies in a typical agricultural value chain. Significant advantages for smallholder farmers include (among others): time and cost savings, convenience, efficient cash management and improved financial identity (transactional records) (GSMA, 2016). On the other hand, agribusiness companies experience lower costs associated with securing and transporting cash, and distributing payments, timely and safer payments to farmers at multiple locations, and mitigating risks (e.g., theft and fraud) associated with handling cash GSMA, (2016)

Despite the potential benefits of financial technology (fin-tech) for farmers, there are significant challenges that hinder its widespread adoption and impact. Limited digital infrastructure, particularly in rural areas, poses a barrier to accessing fin-tech

services. Moreover, a lack of financial literacy and technical skills among farmers may impede their ability to effectively utilize fin-tech tools. Many rice farmers are unaware of the existence and potential benefits of fin-tech tools suitable for the agricultural industry. This hinders their ability to make informed decisions about integrating these technologies into their agricultural operations. Insufficient access to digital infrastructure, including smartphones and internet connectivity, poses a substantial hurdle to the effective adoption of fin-tech solutions.

By addressing these challenges through a comprehensive approach that combines awareness raising, infrastructure development, education and collaborative policy making, it is possible to bridge existing gaps in adoption. The use of financial technology by rice farmers in Anambra State will open the way to better agricultural and economic performance.

This study explored the intersection of fin-tech and rice farming, delving into the awareness and adoption of fin-tech by rice farmers and its impact on their performance with expected outcome for inclusive growth and sustainable development in agriculture.

2.0 Materials and methods

2.1 Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

A Three-stage sampling method was used. Four Local Government Areas (LGA) that has highest rice cultivation were purposively selected. Two villages each were randomly selected from the LGAs, making a total of 8 villages and random sampling of 13 farmers from each village was done. A total of 104 respondents supplied the data used for this study. Qualitative and quantitative data was

collected using well-structured questionnaire. Data was analyzed using descriptive: mean, frequency and percentage, composite score, and inferential statistics: T-test and logit regression model.

2.2 Logit Model:

The determinants of adoption of fin-tech among rice farmers was analyzed using Logit Model. Logit regression model is the relationships between a dichotomous response variable as the dependent variable and a set of independent variables. Logit models estimate the effects of the explanatory variables on a dependent variable with unordered response categories, Komolafe, Nwankwo and Chilaka (2022).

Assuming the probability that rice farmers awareness and adoption of fin-tech (AF) or not (NAF), then the farmers’ empirical models to be estimated is specified as:

$$RF = \mathcal{F}_0 + \mathcal{F}_1 X_1 + \mathcal{F}_2 X_2 + \dots + \mathcal{F}_n X_n + Et \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$NRF = Y_0 + Y_1 X_1 + Y_2 X_2 + \dots + Y_n X_n + Et \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where, AF is rice farmers awareness and adoption of fin-tech, NRF is non-rice farmers awareness and adoption of fin-tech and vectors of respective parameters to be estimated, \mathcal{F} and Y is Vectors of explanatory variables, E = Error terms.

- X_1 = Years of formal education of the farmer (years)
- X_2 = Age of the farmer (years)
- X_3 = Gender of the farmer (Dummy Male = 1 female = 0)
- X_4 = Household size of farmer X_5 = Farm size (Ha)
- X_6 = Farming experience (years)
- X_7 = Remittances

X_8 = Cooperative membership

2.3 Independent T-test

Independent T Test for testing the difference of two means was used to test if there was significant differences in yield between the two groups of farmers (farmers with high awareness and adoption to fin-tech and those with low awareness and adoption)

$$t = \frac{(\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2)}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}\right)}}$$

Where \bar{x}_1 is mean yield of farmers with high level of awareness and adoption of fin-tech.

\bar{x}_2 is mean yield of farmers with low level of awareness and adoption of fin-tech.

- s_1 is mean yield of farmers with high awareness and adoption to fin-tech,
- s_2 is sample variance for yield farmers.
- n_1 is number of farmers with low level awareness and adoption to fin-tech.
- n_2 is number of farmers with high level awareness and adoption to fin-tech.

3.0 RESULT

3.1 Level of awareness of fin-tech among rice farmers

Table 1 showed the mean ratings of the respondents on the five identified variables on methods that could be used to assess the awareness of rice farm about Fin-tech in the study area. Identified variables had mean values ranging from 3.31 to 1.80 on a 3-point rating sale system (POS). The results showed that the farmers were aware of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) ($x = 3.31 + 2.42$), this supported the work of Onovo, and Enwelu (2011). Point of Sales

(POS) ($\bar{X}=3.11+ 1.48$), this result is slightly higher than that of Onyebuchi *et al.*, (2017). They asserted that POS usage in Enugu is ineffective as more than 50% of their responded were unaware of the technology, Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) ($\bar{x}=3.00 + 1.99$), Mobile APPs ($\bar{x}=2.74 + 1.01$) and Online banking ($\bar{x}=1.80 + 1.46$). The overall mean awareness ranking revealed that ATM ($\bar{x}=3.11 + 2.42$) ranked highest, this is possibly because ATM is required for POS

transaction while Online banking ($\bar{x}=1.80 + 0.40$) ranked lowest since, it requires expensive android phone, internet facility and computer literacy. The grand mean rating for rice farmers awareness of fin-tech was ($\bar{x}=2.79$) and the standard deviation was (1.46). The result agrees with Pothula (2022) that Agri-FinTech can only benefit if they recognize this potential and embrace it properly.

Table 1: Level of awareness of fin-tech among rice farmers

FINETECH AWARENESS	Mean	Standard Deviation	Awareness Mean Rating
ATM	3.31	2.42	High awareness
POS	3.11	1.48	High awareness
USSD	3.00	1.99	High awareness
MOBILE APP	2.74	1.01	Average awaren
On-line-banking	1.80	0.40	Low awareness
Grand mean	2.79	1.46	Average awareness

Field survey 2023

3.2 Determinants of adoption of fin-tech among rice farmers

Table 2 presented the Logit model results used to investigate determinants of adoption of fin-tech among rice farmers. Eight variables were modeled, but only four variables were significant at 5%. The likelihood ratio chi-square of 19.72, LR $\chi^2(6) = 79.72$; Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.0031$, Log likelihood = -46.659043 with a p-value of 0.000 and Pseudo $R^2 = 0.1745$ revealed that the model as a whole was statistically significant. Age negatively affected the use of fin-tech among rice farmers. This

implied that with advancement in age there was the likelihood that farmers' adoption of fin-tech reduces. The marginal effect (0.105) meant that with one year increase in the age of farmers there is likelihood of adoption of fin-tech by 5% *ceteris paribus*. This is against the findings of Gupta et al, (2022) that asserted demographic factors such as gender, age and education level were ineffective in influencing adoption of fin tech but agreed with Abdulai Adams (2021) work. Coefficient of sex was negative indicating that been a male enhances the adoption of fin-tech among

rice farmers. Household size significant at 5% positively influenced the use of fin-tech among rice farmers. This implied that with an increase in household size there was likelihood that farmers' adoption of fin-tech increases. The marginal effect (0.061) meant that with one person increase in household size of farmer the likelihood of adoption of fin-tech increase by 5% all other things been equal. Farm size positively influences the use of fin-tech among rice farmers, but it is not significant. Peers/community influence is significant at 5%. With its increase there is the likelihood of an increase in farmers' adoption of fin-tech. This is in line with the work of Amnas *et al.*, (2023) Remittances were significant at 5%, positively influence the use of fin-tech by farmers. This implied that with increased remittances there was likelihood that farmers' adoption of fin-tech increases. The marginal effect (2.44) meant

that with 2.44 increase remittances the likelihood of adoption of fin-tech increased by 5%. Membership of cooperative was significant at 5% and positively influenced the use of fin-tech by farmers. The marginal effect (0.175) meant that with 0.175 increase in membership of cooperative the likelihood of adoption of fin-tech increased by 5%. This agrees with Abdulai Adams (2021) who stated that the variables that are statistically significant in determining adoption of the technologies are the regional location of the farmer, age, educational level, Farmer Based Organization (FBO) membership, and the number of extensions visit. While age, FBO membership, and the number of extensions visit influence adoption positively, regional location, and educational-level influence adoption negatively.

Table 2.: Determinants of adoption of fin-tech among rice farmers

Result of logit model on Adoption of Fin-tech

Logit Regression Result			Marginal effect	
Variables	Coefficient	p> z	Coefficient	p> z
Age	-1.858*	0.008	-0.105	0.017
Sex	-0.225	0.67	-0.236	0.76
Household size	0.401*	0.006	0.061	0.03
Education level	0.806*	0.001	0.065	0.02
Farm size	0.44	0.198	0.006	0.19
Peers/community influence	1.54**	0.032	0.192	0.07
Remittances	3.33**	0.006	2.44	0.08
Coop membership	1.27*	0.04	0.175	0.02

Recommendation

Government, banks, and community should partner to reduce/eliminate the challenges faced by farmers in adopting fin-tech by improving financial inclusion, social amenities that will improve access to internet facilities and fin tech enhancers such as smart phone affordability by farmers. Since there is significant difference in the rice yield of fin-tech adopters and non-adopters every necessary step should be taken by stakeholders to improve the adoption of fin-tech to improve food security in Nigeria.

Therefore, while fin-tech has the potential to enhance financial inclusion and empower farmers, ensuring reliable internet connectivity, facilitating the

supply of affordable smartphones, and establishing community hotspots where farmers can interact with fin-tech platforms, deploy targeted education campaigns to raise rice farmers' awareness of the benefits and functionality of fin-tech solutions. Workshops, community outreach programs, and partnerships with local extension agencies can play an important role in disseminating information. Also, design and implement financial education programs tailored to the specific needs of rice farmers. These programs can enhance their understanding of financial concepts, increase their digital literacy and enable them to use financial technology tools effectively.

3.3 Rice yield differential of fin-tech adopters and non-adopters.

The T-test was conducted to ascertain any significant difference in the rice yield of fin-tech adopters and non-adopters based on the stated null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the rice yield of fin-tech adopters and non-adopters. The result showed significant difference in the

rice yield of fin-tech adopters and non-adopters significant at 1% level of significance. Therefore, the H_0 was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis H_a was accepted. According to Chan, et al (2022), adoption of digital marketplace and Fin-tech contributed to the overall agribusiness sustainability in their study area.

Table 3. T-test to ascertain significant difference in the rice yield of fin-tech adopters and non-adopters.

S	Vari	Mea	Std.	t	Dec
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2	Non	.432	.800		
	-	692	902		
	adop	3	7		
	ters				

4.1 CONCLUSION

The study provides empirical evidence that rice farmers were aware and adopted financial technology (fin-tech) for better performance in Anambra State, Nigeria. The results highlight the importance of awareness as an antecedent to adoption, emphasizing the need for targeted

educational initiatives to familiarize farmers with the potential benefits of these technologies (fin-tech tools). Access to information and technology emerged as a key factor, demonstrating the need to improve digital infrastructure and educational programs to fill existing knowledge gaps.

REFERENCES

- Abdul-Rahman, A., & Abdulai, A. (2022). Mobile money adoption, input use, and farm output among smallholder rice farmers in Ghana. *Agribusiness*, 38, 236–255. <https://doi.org/10.1002/agr.21721>
- Ali, M., Ahmed, S., & Khan, A. (2023). Financial Inclusion and Improved Performance of Rice Farmers: The Role of FinTech Adoption. *Agricultural Informatics*, 18(1), 45-62.
- Amnas, M. B., Selvam, M., Raja, M., Santhoshkumar, S., & Parayitam, S. (2023). Understanding the Determinants of FinTech Adoption: Integrating UTAUT2 with Trust Theoretic Model. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 16(12), 505. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm16120505>
- Chan, A. G., Delim, S. M., Gamayon, D. D., & Tingzon, C. M. (2022). Examining how digital marketplace adoption and fintech adoption contribute to the sustainability of selected small agribusinesses in Metro Manila: A multiple case study approach. https://animorepository.dlsu.edu.ph/etdb_dsi/11.
- Chen, W., & Hu, J. (2019). Barriers and Facilitators of Fin-tech Adoption: A Mixed-Methods Study Among Rice Farmers in China. *Journal of Agricultural and Resource Economics*, 30(1), 55-68.
- Ezeano, C. I., Ume, S. I., Okeke, C. C., & Gbughemobi, B. O. (2017). Socioeconomic Determinant Factors to Youths Participation in Broilers Production in Imo State of Nigeria. *International Journal of Research & Review*, 4(1), 136-142.
- Ernst & Young, (2019), [Global Fintech Adoption Index](#) Report, 2019. EY Assurance, Tax, Transactions and Advisory management Report
- Gbughemobi, B.O., Meludu, N.T and Nkamigbo, D.C. (2021). Socioeconomic determinants and availability of ICT for use among small holder rice farmers in Southeast, Nigeria. *Intl Journal of Environmental and Agriculture Research*, (IJOEAR), 7(9),34-40.
- Goedde, L., Ooko-Ombaka, A., & Pais, G. (2019). Winning in Africa's agricultural market. McKinsey & Company [accessed 20 April 2020]
- GSMA. 2016 The Mobile Economy Report 2016. <https://www.gsma.com>
- Gupta W., Agarwal B., Nautiyal N. (2022). The introduction of financial technologies is an example of Indian MSMEs. *Finance: Theory and Practice*. 26 (6): 192-211. <https://doi.org/10.26794/2587-5671-2022-26-6-192-211>
- Jack, W., and T. Suri. 2014. Risk Sharing and Transactions Costs: Evidence from Kenya's Mobile Money Revolution. *American*

- Economic Review* 104(1): 183–223.
- Komolafe, J.O., & Adeoti A.I., (2018), "Influence of Social Capital on The Use of Improved Maize Seed Among Farmers in Southwestern Nigeria.", *International Journal of Agriculture and Forestry*, 8, (3), Pp 129-138
- Komolafe, Nwankwo and Chilaka (2022). Willingness of Agriculture Students to be Involved in Agripreneur Career in Southeast Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Production*, 3(1), 9-16
- Mbiti, I., and D. N. Weil. 2011. Mobile Banking: The Impact of M-Pesa in Kenya. No. w17129. *National Bureau of Economic Research*.
- McIntosh, C. and C. S. Mansini, 2018. The Use of Financial Technology in the Agriculture Sector. ADBI Working Paper 872. Tokyo: Asian Development Bank Institute. Available : <https://www.adb.org/publications/us-e-financial-technology-agriculture-sector>
- National Bureau of Statistics (2018). Nigeria Gross Domestic Product Report. Government of Nigeria, Nigeria
- Onovo, C. L. and Enwelu, I. A (2011). Farmers' Awareness and Use of Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) in Selected Communities in Enugu North Senatorial Zone, Enugu State *Journal of Agricultural Extension* Vol. 15 (1) , 40 <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/jae.v15i1.5>
- Onyebuchi, A.B., Nwankwo, Simon N, P, Onuka O.I., (2017). Point of Sale (POS) - adoption and Challenges in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Science and Economic Research* 2(2), 203 www.ijsser.org
- Pothula 2022, The Role of Finance in Navigating Agriculture through Agri-FinTech
- Vives, X. (2019). Digital Disruption in Banking. *Annual Review of Financial Economics*, 11(1), 243–272. doi: 10.1146/annurev-financial-100719-120854
- Wang, Q., Nguyen, T., & Le, H. (2017). The Impact of Fin-tech Adoption on Rice Farmers' Performance in Vietnam. *Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 20(3), 112-126.
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